

Valuing the Invisible: Estimating the Preservation Value of Dibru Saikhowa National Park, Assam

Daisy Konwar¹ and Nivedita Goswami²

¹Department of Economics, Dibrugarh University,
Dibrugarh, Assam, INDIA
Email: daisykonwar@dibru.ac.in

²Department of Economics, Gauhati University,
Guwahati, Assam, INDIA
Email: nivedita@gauhati.ac.in

ABSTRACT

Natural ecosystems provide vital services to human societies, many of which are intangible, invisible and excluded from market pricing. Dibru Saikhowa National Park (DSNP), a river-island national park in Assam, India is one such ecologically rich but economically undervalued site. This study estimates the preservation value of DSNP using the Contingent Valuation Method (CVM). Based on a representative sample of 362 households, the study elicits individuals' willingness to pay (WTP) for continued preservation of DSNP, independent of any direct use. To ensure reliability, the survey incorporates rigorous bias-mitigation techniques addressing several biases and anomalies that affect CVM. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) identifies two attitudinal dimensions viz., Warm-glow motive and Preservation motive, out of which only the latter significantly influences WTP. A Tobit regression model reveals that environmental awareness, education, and income positively affect WTP, while age and distance to the site show negative effects. To estimate the total preservation value for the state of Assam, the median monthly WTP was scaled up to all households and annualised. The resulting valuation, when compared with the annual government allocation for the area, reveals that public conservation spending amounts to only 0.013% of the preservation value, highlighting a stark underinvestment in conservation efforts. The findings highlight substantial public support for the non-use values of DSNP and underline the need to integrate such values into environmental budgeting and policy.

Keywords: Contingent valuation, Willingness to pay, Exploratory factor analysis, Tobit estimation.

Mathematics Subject Classification: 62G10, 62F03, 62H12, 62N01, 62P20

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1. INTRODUCTION

The conservation of ecologically significant landscapes in the Global South is increasingly constrained by limited funding and the persistent undervaluation of the ecosystem services they provide. Natural ecosystems such as forests, wetlands, and protected areas offer a range of benefits, including provisioning services like timber and fuelwood, and cultural and recreational services derived from tourism. These are often referred to as *use values* and tend to receive sufficient attention in economic and policy frameworks.

However, beyond these direct or indirect uses, ecosystems also generate a set of *non-use values* that are equally critical but less visible in market transactions. These represent benefits that do not require active interaction with the resource. Their absence in formal accounting frameworks often results in the systematic underrepresentation of certain landscapes in conservation policy and budget allocation. The concept of non-use value, also referred to as preservation value, was formally integrated into mainstream economic thought by John Krutilla in his seminal 1967 essay, *Conservation Reconsidered*. Krutilla contended that individuals do not need to be direct users or consumers of an environmental asset to derive utility from its mere existence. He emphasized that the continued presence of irreplaceable natural features, such as exceptional landscapes or diverse ecosystems, can constitute an essential component of individual well-being. In his words, the preservation of such unique environmental entities contributes meaningfully to the perceived wealth or quality of life for many people (Krutilla, 1967). Consequently, the irreversible loss of such resources, particularly in the absence of comparable alternatives, may result in acute distress and a perceived sense of deprivation among those who value them. In literature, non-use values are often classified into four major components: *Existence value* i.e., the value individuals derive from the mere knowledge that a natural resource or ecosystem continues to exist (Kolstad, 2011). *Option value* i.e., the value of preserving the possibility of using a resource in the future, even though it's not being used currently (Hanely et al., 1997). *Bequest value* i.e., the value associated with conserving a resource for the benefit of future generations (Kolstad, 2011). *Altruistic value* i.e., the value associated with the satisfaction gained from knowing that others in the current generation can benefit from the resource (Kolstad, 2011). These ethical and intergenerational considerations are central to public support for environmental protection but remain empirically invisible and therefore under-measured, especially in the context of developing countries.

One of the most widely accepted tools to estimate such values is the Contingent Valuation Method (CVM), a stated preference approach that directly elicits individuals' Willingness to Pay (WTP) for hypothetical conservation scenarios. The present study applies CVM to estimate the preservation value, defined as an aggregate of non-use values, of the Dibru Saikhowa National Park (DSNP), a unique but underfunded protected area in Assam, India. The primary objective is to estimate the monetary value that individuals assign through their WTP to the continued preservation of DSNP in the absence of current use. In doing so, the study also seeks to identify the socio-economic and attitudinal factors that significantly influence individuals' WTP, and to assess whether the stated valuations reflect sufficient public support to enhance existing conservation efforts in terms of increased budgetary allocation.

2. BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

The DSNP, located in the floodplains of the Brahmaputra and Dibru rivers in Assam, holds a distinct ecological significance. It is the only river-island national park in India. Originally declared a wildlife sanctuary, its status was upgraded to a National Park in 1999 with a specific mandate to conserve the endangered White-winged Wood Duck (*Asarcornis scutulata*), which is also the state bird of Assam. The park forms the core area of the Dibru Saikhowa Biosphere Reserve and lies within the Indo-Burma global biodiversity hotspot. It has been designated as an Important Bird Area (IBA) due to its

significance in migratory flyways. The park includes many species listed as endangered or threatened under the IUCN Red List. Notable among these are the Bengal Slow Loris (*Nycticebus bengalensis*), and the Gangetic River Dolphin (*Platanista gangetica*). The park supports a rich mix of aquatic and terrestrial life, including around 500 species of Birds (Mahanta, 2014). In addition, many invertebrate species found in the area have yet to be formally studied or documented. DSNP is also home to a feral horse population of historical significance.

Despite its ecological importance, DSNP remains underrepresented in national and state conservation strategies. In contrast to parks like Kaziranga or Manas which are widely celebrated for their flagship megafauna like tigers and rhinoceros, DSNP is not known for such species and receives limited tourist attention. This invisibility translates into budgetary neglect, making the park particularly vulnerable to ecological degradation. The threats to DSNP are multiple and compounding: seasonal flooding, soil erosion, illegal encroachments, deforestation, unregulated grazing, and pollution from nearby industrial sites are a few examples. The blowout at an Oil India Limited (OIL) gas well in 2020 located near the park and the consequent efforts and struggle of the government for providing compensation to those adversely affected, highlighted the urgent need for robust valuation frameworks that can inform compensation, restoration, and mitigation efforts. In this context, estimating the non-use value of DSNP becomes essential. Since the park's economic significance is not adequately reflected through tourism revenue, it becomes necessary to gauge public support for its continued preservation through a stated preference framework. CVM offers a direct method to assign monetary value to these otherwise intangible benefits.

CVM has been widely used to estimate the economic value of protected areas, particularly in contexts where tourism or recreational use dominates. Studies such as those by Shultz et al. (1998) and Lee and Han (2002) demonstrate that visitors often express a WTP more than existing fees, reflecting strong public support for conservation when recreational benefits are clearly perceived. Some researchers have extended the use of CVM to assess broader ecological and preservation values. For example, studies from Indonesia and Brazil have shown that conservation-based management scenarios tend to yield greater overall value compared to exploitative or mixed-use approaches (van Beukering et al., 2003; Adams et al., 2008). These findings highlight the usefulness of CVM not just for valuing tourism, but for capturing the non-market benefits of ecological protection. In India, however, CVM applications to forest resources have largely remained focused on well-known parks with significant tourism potential. Earlier studies on Borivli, Khangchendzonga and Kaziranga National Parks have shown that people are willing to support conservation financially, particularly when sites are visible and attract interests of the visitors (Hadker et al., 1997; Maharana et al., 2000; Barman, 2012). Similar findings have been reported in other Indian contexts. For instance, Rajkumar and Boopathi (2020) estimated visitors' WTP for a higher entrance fee at the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve in Tamil Nadu and found that 72% of visitors were willing to pay more, with education, occupation, and income as significant predictors of WTP. Bhatt, Shah, and Abdullah (2014) evaluated local residents' WTP for preserving wetland biodiversity in the Pongdam Wetland of Himachal Pradesh, revealing strong community support for joint management approaches. Likewise, De and Devi (2013) applied CVM at Cherrapunjee, Meghalaya and found that visitors were willing to pay for both recreational enjoyment and conservation

of the site, emphasizing the dual economic and ecological benefits of natural areas. Collectively, these studies affirm that Indian visitors increasingly recognize the importance of financially supporting conservation when environmental and recreational values are tangible and locally relevant.

From the above discussion it is observed that the use of CVM to measure the economic value of protected areas has largely been limited to tourism-centric sites, with little attention given to ecologically important areas that lack flagship species or revenue-generating potential. DSNP offers a compelling case for such an application since it is ecologically vital, legally protected, yet economically overlooked. By estimating the park's preservation value, this study aims to provide an empirical basis for enhancing public investment and strengthening legal protection. Furthermore, a large body of empirical studies overlook key methodological concerns in CVM, such as various biases and anomalies arising from the hypothetical nature of the market, which reduces the reliability of their findings. This study addresses these limitations through a more rigorous survey design and statistical techniques. It also examines psychological motivations such as warm-glow and preservationist attitudes as additional determinants of WTP by incorporating attitudinal measures and applying factor analysis to uncover underlying motivational patterns. This approach aims to provide a more nuanced understanding of conservation preferences that go beyond standard socioeconomic variables. Through this combination of improved methodology and expanded conceptual framing, the study aims to make a meaningful contribution to both policy making and academic understanding of ecosystem valuation in underfunded conservation contexts.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Data and Sampling Design

The necessary secondary data for the study were obtained through a visit to the Guijan Range Office of the Tinsukia Wildlife Division. However, no fieldwork was conducted within or in the immediate vicinity of DSNP for the purpose of the present work. The primary survey for this study was conducted in 2017. The survey involved no physical intervention, clinical procedures, or engagement with vulnerable populations. Informed and voluntary consent was obtained from all participants after explaining the study's purpose. Respondents' anonymity and confidentiality were ensured throughout, and no personally identifying information was collected. The relevant population for the study has been identified as the state of Assam. A multi-stage random sampling design was adopted for the CVM survey. Given the commonly observed *distance decay* effect in environmental valuation literature, where individuals' WTP tends to decline or decay with increasing distance from the environmental resource, the initial stage of sampling involved categorizing the districts of Assam based on their proximity to DSNP. All 27 districts of Assam as per the Census of India 2011¹ were ranked by the shortest road distance from their respective district headquarters to the park. These were then grouped into three categories: the nine nearest districts, the nine most distant, and the nine in between. One district was then randomly selected from each group: Tinsukia (nearest), Nagaon (intermediate), and Bongaigaon (most distant).

In the second stage, one revenue circle was randomly chosen from each district. The circles that were selected are Tinsukia (Tinsukia district), Kaliabor (Nagaon district), and Sidli Part II (Bongaigaon district)². In the third stage, two villages or towns were selected from each circle: Tinsukia town and Bordubi from Tinsukia, Jakhalabandha and Silghat from Kaliabor, and BRPL Township and Dhaligaon from Sidli Part II.

In the final stage, approximately equal numbers of households were selected from each location at random: 61 from Tinsukia town, 60 from Bordubi, 60 each from Jakhalabandha and Silghat, 61 from BRPL Township and 60 from Dhaligaon. Hence, the final sample size becomes 362. The household serves as the primary unit of observation, and data were collected through direct interaction with the head of the household or, in their absence, an adult member (18 years or older) capable of making decisions on behalf of the household.

3.2 Setting Up the Hypothetical Market for CVM

To operationalise CVM, a hypothetical market is constructed in the absence of a real one, in which respondents express their WTP for the good being valued. Do to so, in our study, the respondents were first presented with standard information on the park's ecological significance and existing threats, supported by photographs to ensure a uniform understanding. Following this, a proposed conservation plan was introduced, outlining specific interventions aimed at addressing key ecological challenges. It was made clear that the plan's implementation would require additional funding from the public. The scenario was framed exclusively in terms of non-use benefits, deliberately excluding any recreational or direct-use aspects. Respondents were then asked about their WTP as a voluntary contribution to support the proposed conservation efforts. This setup enabled the estimation of non-use values, including existence, option, altruistic, and bequest values within a well-defined hypothetical market structure.

3.3 Elicitation Format and Bid Design

The study employed a combination of Single-bounded Dichotomous Choice (DC) and Open-Ended elicitation methods to enhance methodological robustness and allow for cross-validation of WTP estimates. The use of both formats provides complementary advantages. While the DC format closely replicates real-world decision-making, the open-ended format offers more detailed, individual-level welfare measures (Freeman III et al., 2014).

In the DC format, each respondent was presented with a fixed bid amount, defined as the hypothetical monetary contribution required to support the proposed conservation plan, and asked whether they would be willing to pay that amount. As a response, the respondent only had to say "yes" or "no". This is a take-it-or-leave-it structure, closer to real life decision making in the conventional market which reduces cognitive burden and improves response reliability (Bateman et al., 2001; Freeman III et al., 2014). To determine a suitable bid vector, a pilot survey of 42 households was conducted beforehand, using an open-ended WTP question. Responses in the pilot ranged from ₹30 to ₹400. Based on these

results, five bid values were selected for the final survey: ₹20, ₹50, ₹100, ₹200, and ₹500. The lowest (₹20) and the highest (₹500) bids of the final bid vector were set slightly beyond the observed minimum and maximum in the pilot to ensure a wider coverage since the final sample was many times larger than the pilot sample. ₹50 was chosen for having the highest frequency among bids below the mode in the pilot, while ₹100 being the modal value in the pilot was used as the central bid. ₹200 was selected as the most frequent bid above the mode in the pilot. In the final survey, out of 362 respondents, 243 accepted or responded “yes” to the proposed bid amounts. The proportion of “yes” responses generally declined with increasing bid values, in accordance with the law of demand⁹. This consistency supports the internal validity of the bid design, indicating that respondents engaged meaningfully with the valuation scenario.

The open-ended question, administered alongside the DC format, was to ask respondents to specify the maximum amount they would be willing to pay viz., their Maximum Willingness to Pay (MWTP) per month over a period of five years to support the implementation of the proposed plan. This format enables a more granular understanding of individual preferences and serves as a useful complement to the binary DC responses, thereby enhancing the credibility of WTP estimates.

3.4 Bias Mitigation Methods

Since CVM relies on hypothetical scenarios to elicit preferences, it is particularly susceptible to various forms of biases and anomalies. Identifying and mitigating these biases is essential to ensure that the stated WTP values reflect genuine preferences and are reliable for policy use. Following are the bias mitigation methods used in the study.

3.4.1 Mitigation of Hypothetical bias: Hypothetical bias, common in CVM studies, arises when respondents overstate their WTP due to the lack of real financial consequences (List and Gallet, 2001; Loomis, 2014). To address this, the study applied a two-step correction to the DC responses: a *Reality Check* followed by *Uncertainty Recoding*. After each “yes” response, participants were reminded that any payment would reduce their disposable income and that other environmental causes might also require their support, prompting them to reconsider budget constraints. They were then asked to rate their certainty about the “yes” response, on a scale from 1 (very uncertain) to 10 (very certain). Only responses with a certainty level of 7 or higher were retained as “yes” and the rest were converted to “No”. This ex-post method is empirically regarded as effective in aligning hypothetical responses with actual behaviour (Ethier et al., 2000; Blumenschein et al., 2008; Morrison and Brown, 2009). This reduced the number of “yes” responses from 243 to 175, suggesting that 68 “yes” responses were influenced by hypothetical bias. The corrected responses, called the hypothetical bias (HB) corrected “yes” responses, show a clear inverse relationship between the bid amount and WTP, consistent with the law of demand, further supporting the internal validity of the bid structure. For open-ended responses, MWTP was collected only after applying the same reality check and recoding, supporting the claim that they are also free from hypothetical bias.

3.4.2 Checking for Anchoring effect: In CVM studies, anchoring effect refers to a situation where respondents may base their stated WTP on the value suggested to them earlier in the survey, rather than on their own independent judgment. Although anchoring usually does not affect open-ended questions, it can still appear when such questions follow a Dichotomous Choice (DC) question that presents a specific bid amount. To check for the existence of this bias, the open-ended WTP question in this study was presented immediately after the DC question. Since the DC question used randomly assigned bids ₹20, ₹50, ₹100, ₹200, and ₹500, there was a possibility that these values could influence respondents' answers to the following open-ended question. To test for this effect, the *Kruskal–Wallis* test is conducted using SPSS. The test is applied to examine whether there is any statistically significant difference in the MWTP values reported in the open-ended format, across the five subgroups, based on the bid value presented in the DC question.

3.5 Extraction of Motivational Factors

To examine the psychological drivers of WTP, 12 attitudinal items are included in the survey, each rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). These items, developed through literature review and pilot testing, aim to capture ethical, emotional, and altruistic motivations related to conservation. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) is conducted using SPSS to identify the underlying motivational factors, as no a priori factor structure was assumed (Fabrigar and Wegener, 2012; Thompson, 2004). The suitability of data is assessed using the KMO measure and Bartlett's test of sphericity. Factors are extracted using the Kaiser criterion (eigenvalue >1) and rotated via Varimax. The analysis reveals two interpretable motivational dimensions: one reflecting emotional/social rewards from giving, and another representing a preservationist orientation. Internal consistency is assessed with Cronbach's alpha. Factor scores are then computed and used as regressors in the Tobit model to evaluate their influence on WTP.

3.6 Model Specification for Identifying the Determinants of WTP

The choice of model for identifying the determinants WTP in any CVM study basically depends on two things: first, the choice between DC and open-ended responses and second, the treatment of protest bids⁴. The present study chooses the open-ended responses over the DC responses to estimate WTP, as open-ended formats, when free of bias and anomalies, offer more precise, individual-level data. While DC questions are included, their primary role is to: (a) reduce hypothetical bias in subsequent open-ended responses; (b) serve as a comparative reference for bias correction; and (c) provide an auxiliary validation of open-ended WTP estimates. However, DC formats yield limited information, as they only indicate whether WTP is above or below a specified bid amount. This constrains the accuracy of estimation and makes results highly sensitive to survey design, distributional assumptions, and functional form (Hanley et al., 1997; Haab and McConnell, 2002). Given the application of rigorous bias-reducing measures, the open-ended responses are deemed reliable in the study and used for further

analysis. These responses are also cross-validated against the HB corrected DC responses, which showed consistency.

A further consideration in model specification is the treatment of protest bids. Out of 362 respondents, 36 reported zero WTP. Among them, 23 respondents are identified as protest bidders based on their selected reasons of non-payment. Although exclusion of protest bid is sometimes followed, it comes with drawbacks. Prior studies caution that such deletions may induce selection bias and undermine sample representativeness, as protest bids often reflect systematically related views rather than random anomalies (Halstead et al., 1992; Jorgensen and Syme, 2000; Frey and Pirscher 2019). Therefore, to retain the integrity of the sample and to reflect a more comprehensive range of respondent perspectives, protest bids are retained in the final dataset. The inclusion of 36 zero-WTP responses gives rise to a corner solution outcome, where WTP is zero for part of the sample and continuously distributed above zero for the rest (Wooldridge, 2013). Since the actual WTP for protest bidders remains unobserved, the data are treated as left-censored, with MWTP values observed for some respondents and censored at zero for others. In such censored samples, while explanatory variables are fully observed, the dependent variable is only partially observed (Gujarati, 2015). To account for this censoring, a *Tobit* model is employed.

The Tobit model expresses the observed variable, y , in terms of an underlying latent variable, y^* .

$$y^* = \beta_0 + \mathbf{x}\boldsymbol{\beta} + u, \quad u | \mathbf{x} \sim \text{Normal}(0, \sigma^2)$$

And, $y = y^*$ when $y^* \geq 0$,
 $y = 0$ when $y^* < 0$

Here, \mathbf{x} denotes the set of explanatory variables, and $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ represents their associated slope coefficients. The unobserved latent variable y^* is assumed to follow the standard assumptions of classical linear regression model. Given that y^* follows a normal distribution, the observed variable y is continuously distributed over positive values. For observations where y is greater than zero, its conditional density mirrors that of y^* given \mathbf{x} (Wooldridge, 2013).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Anchoring Effect

No evidence of anchoring is found, despite the open-ended WTP question being asked immediately after a DC question with specific bid amounts suggested. The Kruskal–Wallis test shows that the differences in MWTP across the five bid groups are not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 4.963$, $p = 0.291$), indicating that the suggested bids did not influence respondents' stated values [results presented in table 1].

Table 1: Summary of Kruskal–Wallis test for detecting Anchoring effect:

Test & Purpose	H ₀	Statistic (p)	Result
Kruskal–Wallis: Anchoring Effect (Open-ended)	MWTP is same across all bid groups.	4.963 (0.291)	H ₀ not rejected

Source: Author's analysis based on survey data.

This suggests that respondents did not systematically anchor their valuations to the initial bid they received. The absence of anchoring may be attributed to the inclusion of a reality check, which reminded participants to consider income constraints and alternative options, prompting more deliberate and independent responses.

4.2 Assessment of other Biases and Anomalies in WTP Responses

In addition to hypothetical bias and anchoring, the study also takes account of several other issues that often affect CVM responses. It is worth noting that the present study uses the same dataset as an earlier work by the authors (Konwar and Goswami, 2019), which was confined to testing information bias and free-riding behaviour in CVM. The finding in that earlier work that neither of those biases was significant after appropriate corrections, provides an added layer of confidence in the validity of the present data. Building on that foundation, the current analysis extends the bias assessment to cover *yea-saying*, *payment vehicle bias*, and potential *strategic* responses.

Yea-saying, or the tendency to agree with any bid regardless of the value, is addressed through the same reality check adopted to reduce hypothetical bias. Of the 243 initial “yes” responses in the DC format, 68 are revised to “no” after uncertainty recoding, suggesting that *yea-saying* is effectively filtered out. *Payment vehicle bias* is also considered, as differences in WTP can sometimes arise from the choice of payment mode, specially when the suggested payment mode is not favourable to the respondents (Morrison et al., 2000). To avoid this, respondents in the present study are given the option to choose their preferred mode of payment, either through a mandatory tax or a voluntary contribution. Besides, none of the 36 non-payers cited ‘dissatisfaction with the payment mode’ as reasons for their non-payment, indicating that the vehicle itself was not a source of bias.

Finally, the possibility of *strategic bias* is also considered. Such bias may arise when respondents deliberately and strategically state unusually high or low bids to influence survey outcomes, producing extreme values that may sway the sample average in their desired direction. In this study, to minimise the influence of extreme values and thereby the influence of potential strategic behaviour, the Median is adopted to compute the sample average WTP rather than the Mean. Being less sensitive to outliers, the Median provides a more reliable representation of average WTP.

Taken together, these checks, along with the earlier tests for information bias and free-riding behaviour reported in Konwar and Goswami (2019), strengthen the overall credibility and robustness of the WTP estimates used in this study.

4.3 Results of EFA

The initial EFA was conducted on 12 attitudinal items designed to capture the psychological motivations of the respondents for supporting the preservation of DSNP. The items are:

S1: I would like to see our government giving more support to organisations that are promoting work in the field of environmental preservation.

S2: It is difficult for me to decline assistance to people who beg for charity.

S3: Even though I may never visit the DSNP, I would be happy to see it protected, so that other people from different parts of the world can visit the park and observe wildlife in its natural habitat.

S4: I feel the wildlife of DSNP has a right to exist in their natural habitat even though they may not be of any use to mankind.

S5: It is hard for me to refuse to pay a donation if the fundraisers are known to me, because of social or peer pressure.

S6: Even though I may never see a White Winged Wood Duck in its natural habitat, I would be happy to know that it is kept safe from extinction, so that our future generations would be able to see it.

S7: I admire people who, voluntarily participate in collecting donations for social aid and solidarity.

S8: Giving blood is giving life.

S9: Even though I may not experience the rich biodiversity of DSNP, I would still like to contribute towards its preservation so that I have a chance to see it someday in the future.

S10: I feel happy whenever I contribute to a social cause.

S11: Irrespective of the fact that whether or not I or anybody visit this national park, I will want it to be protected.

S12: I like to spend my holidays outdoor amidst nature, rather than spending it indoor.

As the part of initial analysis for EFA, sampling adequacy was confirmed using the KMO statistic (0.770) and Bartlett's test of sphericity ($\chi^2 = 1803.561$, $p < 0.001$). However, based on low communality scores (less than 0.5) and weak loadings, three items (S1, S8, and S12) were removed. A second EFA was run on the remaining nine items. The KMO improved to 0.826 and Bartlett's test remained significant ($\chi^2 = 2180.000$, $p < 0.001$), supporting the suitability of the data. The communalities of the retained items are all above 0.5 [results presented in table 2], indicating good shared variance.

Table 2: Communalities of the Retained Items

Items	Initial	Extraction
S2	.716	.755
S3	.610	.626
S4	.499	.556
S5	.786	.820
S6	.459	.508
S7	.658	.689
S9	.483	.501
S10	.809	.856
S11	.641	.743

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring

Source: Author's analysis based on survey data.

After that, two factors with eigenvalues greater than 1 were extracted, explaining 67.28% of the total variance. Varimax rotation was applied to improve interpretability, resulting in a clear factor structure where all items loaded strongly above the threshold of 0.70 (Comrey and Lee, 1992) on their respective factors, with no significant cross-loadings [results presented in table 3].

Table 3: Rotated factor matrix

Items	Factor 1	Factor 2
S10	.925	
S5	.906	
S2	.867	
S7	.827	
S11		.861
S3		.791
S4		.746
S6		.713
S9		.707

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring

Source: Author's analysis based on survey data.

The first factor includes S10, S5, S2, and S7, items that reflect emotional reward, social pressure, and admiration for charitable acts. This is interpreted as the *Warm-glow* motive, referring to the personal satisfaction from giving (Andreoni, 1990). The second factor includes S11, S3, S4, S6, and S9, which highlight non-use values, independent of current use. This is labelled the *Preservation* motive. Reliability analysis shows high internal consistency for both factors. Cronbach's Alpha is 0.932 for Warm-glow and 0.874 for Preservation, both well above the 0.70 threshold (Nunnally, 1978), confirming that each factor is internally coherent. These two factors, Warm-glow and Preservation, reflect distinct

motivational patterns underlying WTP responses. By identifying them through EFA, the study connects specific attitudinal dimensions to broader psychological drivers of valuation for non-market environmental goods like DSNP. Such internal motives, whether based on emotional reward or a conservation ethic, are known to shape responses in contingent valuation settings (Spash et al., 2009).

Factor scores are then computed for all respondents and used as predictors in the Tobit regression model for WTP. This allows the model to account not only for socioeconomic factors but also for deeper psychological motivations driving conservation preferences.

4.4 Determinants of WTP

A Tobit regression is conducted to estimate the determinants of individuals' MWTP for preservation of DSNP. The censored nature of the dependent variable, where MWTP is zero for some observations and continuously distributed for others, warrants the use of this model. In context of this, the regression model framed for the current study is:

$$MWTP^* = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EAI + \beta_2 AGE + \beta_3 GEN + \beta_4 EDN + \beta_5 LOC + \beta_6 CSI + \beta_7 PASTV + \beta_8 DIST + \beta_9 SUBDIS + \beta_{10} WARM + \beta_{11} PRE + u$$

where, $MWTP^*$ is the latent or the desired variable, a part of which is not observed,

and, $MWTP = MWTP^*$ when $MWTP^* \geq 0$,

$MWTP = 0$ when $MWTP^* < 0$

The description of the explanatory variables included in the model is given below:

Environmental awareness is measured using an Environmental Awareness Index (EAI) constructed from nine Likert-scale items capturing environmental concern and awareness. Each response is scored from 0 to 4, and the negatively worded items were reverse-coded. The total score ranges from 0 to 36, where higher values indicate greater awareness. For comparability, the index for each respondent is calculated as the ratio of their total score to the maximum possible score. The index ranges from 0 to 1 with higher values indicating greater environmental awareness. EAI is expected to have a positive association with MWTP.

Age (AGE), measured in completed years, may influence WTP either positively or negatively depending on generational attitudes. Gender (GEN), a dummy variable, coded as 1 for male and 0 for female, is included to capture any gender-based variation. Education (EDN), measured in years of schooling, is expected to positively influence WTP through better understanding of environmental benefits. Location of residence (LOC) is included as another dummy variable, with urban respondents coded as 1 and rural as 0. No clear directional relationship with WTP is assumed for LOC.

The Consumption Standard Index (CSI), is constructed based on ownership of six specific consumer durables: colour television, electric fan, refrigerator, car, washing machine and air conditioner. The index is used as a proxy for income, since respondents usually don't prefer to disclose direct information about their incomes, and it ranges from 0 (no item owned) to 1 (all items owned). For each respondent, the CSI is calculated as the number of items owned divided by six. Given that environmental quality is

generally considered a normal good, respondents with higher CSI values are expected to have higher WTP for conservation.

Table 4: VIFs of the explanatory variables

Variables	VIF values
Environmental Awareness Index, EAI	1.145
Age of the respondent, AGE	1.032
Gender of the respondent, GEN	1.035
Education of the respondent, EDN	1.536
Location of residence, LOC	1.071
Consumption Standard Index, CSI	1.335
Past visit to DSNP, PASTV	1.076
Distance to the site, DIST	1.067
Distance to the nearest substitute site, SUBDIS	1.083
Warm-glow factor, WARM	1.004
Preservation factor, PRE	1.259

Source: Author's analysis based on survey data.

Past visit to DSNP (PASTV), a dummy variable coded 1 for yes and 0 for no, is included to test whether personal experience may increase MWTP through emotional or experiential attachment. Distance to the site (DIST), in kilometres, is expected to negatively affect WTP due to the distance-decay effect, while distance to the nearest substitute site (SUBDIS) is expected to have a positive effect, as greater distance implies fewer close alternatives, thereby increasing the perceived value of DSNP.

Finally, two attitudinal factors derived from EFA are included: the Warm-glow motive (WARM), capturing intrinsic satisfaction from contributing to a cause, and the Preservation motive (PRE), representing various non-use values. Both are expected to be positively associated with MWTP.

Before estimating the regression model, the data are examined for potential issues of multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity. To assess the presence of multicollinearity, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values are computed. All VIFs are found to be well below the commonly accepted threshold of 5 [results presented in table 4], indicating that the independent variables do not exhibit strong linear correlations with each other and are therefore suitable for inclusion in the regression analysis.

To examine whether heteroscedasticity is present in the model, the Breusch-Pagan (BP) test is performed. The results reveal a chi-square statistic of 238.62 with a p-value of less than 0.01, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity. This indicates that heteroscedasticity is present in the model. To address this issue and ensure the robustness of the estimated standard errors, the regression is estimated using White's heteroscedasticity consistent standard errors (Wooldridge, 2013).

After running these preliminary diagnostics, the Tobit regression model is estimated, and the results are presented in Table 5. The F-statistic in the table is significant at the 1% level, suggesting a good model fit.

Table 5: Results of Tobit estimation and Marginal Effects of the Significant Variables on Observed MWTP

Variables	Coefficients (t-value)	Marginal Effects
EAI	117.84 (3.85) ***	96.03
AGE	- 0.77 (- 2.41) **	- 0.63
GEN	- 3.49 (- 0.40)	-
EDN	5.64 (4.77) ***	4.59
LOC	3.58 (0.39)	-
CSI	79.09 (4.31) ***	64.45
PASTV	3.17 (0.38)	-
DIST	- 0.10 (- 5.08) ***	- 0.08
SUBDIS	0.01 (0.59)	-
WARM	- 2.00 (- 0.60)	-
PRE	56.36 (10.37) ***	45.92
Constant	- 25.12 (- 0.83)	-
Number of observations = 362 F [11, 351] = 19.96***		

Note: *** and ** indicate significance at the 0.01 and 0.05 levels, respectively.

Source: Author's analysis based on survey data.

In Tobit regression, the reported coefficients reflect the marginal effect of the explanatory variables on the latent (unobserved) dependent variable, in this case, MWTP*. However, the primary interest lies in understanding how changes in explanatory variables affect the observed MWTP. Since observed MWTP is censored at zero, these effects are smaller in magnitude. To estimate them, the Tobit coefficients are multiplied by an adjustment factor between zero and one⁵, which scales down their size but not their direction. The resulting marginal effects indicate the expected change in observed MWTP for a one-unit change in the explanatory variable.

Among the explanatory variables, six are found to significantly affect MWTP for the preservation of DSNP. EAI shows a strong positive relationship with MWTP, significant at the 1% level. This reflects that individuals who are more aware of environmental issues tend to better understand the ecological value of the park and are therefore more willing to support its preservation financially. EDN also has a significant positive effect, suggesting that increased educational attainment enhances one's ability to comprehend the importance of conservation, thereby raising their MWTP. CSI, used as a proxy for income, is another significant positive predictor. This is consistent with standard economic theory, where higher income or consumption capacity translates into a greater ability and willingness to pay. AGE, on the other hand, is negatively associated with MWTP. This may indicate that younger individuals, having grown up with greater exposure to environmental challenges, are more concerned

about long-term ecological sustainability and thus assign higher value to conservation efforts. DIST shows a significant negative effect, supporting the distance decay hypothesis. Naturally, people living in closer proximity to an environmental resource are more familiar with the benefits it provides and the problems it faces, which may heighten their concern for its protection. Finally, the PRE factor is highly significant and positively associated with MWTP. This implies that individuals with stronger non-use values are more likely to express support for preservation through higher stated WTP.

The variables GEN, LOC, PASTV, SUBDIS and WARM are not statistically significant. The insignificance of GEN and LOC suggests that support for conservation is not influenced by demographic or spatial differences. Similarly, the lack of effect from PASTV implies that MWTP reflects a non-use or preservation value, independent of direct recreational use in the past. The insignificance of the SUBDIS variable suggests that DSNP may be perceived as ecologically unique, offering environmental services that are not easily replaced by nearby alternatives. In other words, it indicates that DSNP may not have a close substitute site. Interestingly, WARM, the internal satisfaction or moral reward from contributing, is also not significant. This is likely due to the corrective steps taken in the survey, including the reality check and hypothetical bias adjustments, which may have neutralised the emotional overstatement of values commonly associated with warm-glow. This outcome strengthens the claim that the stated values are largely rational and policy-relevant. Additionally, the constant term is not significant, indicating that the combined mean effect of omitted variables is statistically indistinguishable from zero.

4.5 Estimation of Preservation Value of DSNP

The sample average MWTP is calculated using Median, as it is less influenced by extreme values than Mean. Median also helps avoid possible overstatement due to strategic responses. The Median MWTP is found to be ₹100 per household per month. To estimate the total preservation value of DSNP for the state of Assam, the Median monthly MWTP is multiplied by the total number of households in Assam, as per the 2011 Census (63,67,295 households), and then annualised. The resulting estimate yields an aggregated preservation value of ₹764.07 crores per year over a five year period. This figure provides a monetary benchmark for assessing the worth of conservation investments and justifying public or policy support for DSNP.

The annual government allocation for conservation and maintenance of protected areas under the Tinsukia Wildlife Division, which includes DSNP, was ₹9.61 lakhs in 2016–17, the year immediately preceding the period of field survey (Office of the Divisional Forest Officer, Tinsukia Wildlife Division, Tinsukia 2017). This figure serves as the most contextually appropriate benchmark for comparison, as it reflects the policy and funding environment respondents were aware of, while expressing their WTP. When compared to the total preservation value estimated in this study, this allocation amounts to just 0.013% of the total preservation value, highlighting a stark underinvestment in conservation efforts. Given the stable nature of non-use values over time (Carson et al., 2001), this funding gap remains relevant and continues to reflect the shortfall between public support for conservation and actual budgetary commitment.

5. CONCLUSION

The study offers the first comprehensive estimation of the preservation value of DSNP using CVM in a comparatively less-tourist centric, underfunded conservation context in India. The findings reveal that the public assigns significant value to the park's continued protection. This valuation far exceeds the existing public allocations and emphasizes the extent to which ecologically vital but economically invisible landscapes are undervalued in policy. The empirical analysis highlights several key determinants of MWTP. Environmental awareness emerged as one of the strongest predictors, suggesting that MWTP is closely tied to levels of ecological or environmental awareness. Education and consumption standards also showed significant positive effects, indicating that both cognitive understanding and economic capacity shape preferences and hence MWTP. Conversely, age and distance to the site exerted negative influences, supporting the generational shift towards stronger environmental consciousness among younger cohorts and the spatial decay of environmental concern with increasing distance from the resource. Importantly, the preservation motive, extracted through Exploratory Factor Analysis, was found to be a highly significant attitudinal driver of MWTP, reaffirming that the public's valuation of DSNP is anchored not in direct use, but in ethical, altruistic, and existence-based motivations. The insignificance of the warm-glow factor further indicates that responses were guided less by emotional gratification and more by reasoned concern for ecological continuity. The absence of anchoring, information, free-riding, and hypothetical biases, together with the robustness of the Tobit model, lends high credibility to these findings. The median household MWTP of ₹100 per month translates into a preservation value of ₹764.07 crores annually for Assam, an amount several orders of magnitude higher than the current public investment in the area of the park. This enormous gap highlights a clear societal willingness to support conservation financially, if appropriate institutional mechanisms were in place. Such evidence of latent public demand provides a compelling case for the integration of non-use values into conservation budgeting and compensation frameworks.

These insights can be translated into policy actions. There is a clear need to incorporate non-use values into funding decisions, particularly for protected areas like DSNP that, despite having a modest tourism base, do not attract the volume or visibility associated with other national parks in Assam with flagship megafauna. Relying solely on visitor-driven revenues risks overlooking ecologically significant landscapes that attract less visitors but generate substantial non-market benefits. On the basis of findings from the study, mechanisms such as earmarked contributions or biodiversity levies could be explored to operationalize public support. Additionally, expanding environmental education and communication can further strengthen the public's engagement with conservation beyond charismatic species or popular destinations.

Some limitations, however, remain in the study. The contingent nature of stated preferences, though methodologically corrected, still carries hypothetical elements. Moreover, both the funding benchmark (from 2016–17) and the survey data (2017) are slightly dated. However, they still remain relevant, as they reflect stable public attitudes and budgetary conditions around the time of major ecological disturbances in DSNP. Nonetheless, future research may revisit these estimates using updated

datasets and incorporate mixed-methods or longitudinal designs to track evolving conservation preferences over time.

6. REFERENCES

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¹ For the purpose of extrapolating sample estimates to the population level, household data from Census 2011 has been used, as it remains the most recent comprehensive and officially recognized source of disaggregated demographic data in India. While more recent population estimates may exist through projections or local administrative sources, these are often inconsistent, not always publicly available at the micro level, or lack methodological transparency. In contrast, the Census 2011 provides a standardized, nationally endorsed dataset that supports replicability, comparability, and methodological rigor, especially important when calculating aggregate non-use values across diverse geographical regions.

² At the time of district selection, Sidli Part II revenue circle was recorded under Bongaigaon district in the District Census Handbook of India 2011, which served as the sampling frame for this study. However, during fieldwork, it was found that the circle had been administratively shifted to Chirang district. Despite this administrative update, the original classification under Bongaigaon has been retained in the sampling framework to maintain methodological consistency with the census data used for extrapolation purposes.

³ The law of demand tells that other things remaining constant, whenever price of a good increases, its demand falls. Here demand is represented by the “yes” responses, since by agreeing to pay the price (offered bid), people are showing their demand for an improvement in DSNP.

⁴ Protest bids refer to responses in which individuals, despite valuing the good in question, report a zero willingness to pay or withhold a response due to disagreement with the survey design, payment vehicle, or broader policy context (Halstead, 1992).

⁵ The adjustment factor is $\frac{\partial E(y|y > 0, \mathbf{x})}{\partial x_j} = \beta_j \left\{ 1 - \lambda \left(\frac{x_j \beta}{\sigma} \right) \left[\frac{x_j \beta}{\sigma} + \lambda \left(\frac{x_j \beta}{\sigma} \right) \right] \right\}$, where, λ is the ratio between the standard normal pdf and the standard normal cdf (Wooldridge, 2013).